

FINAL YEAR PROJECT THESIS

NAME:	Gregory Hawkes
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SUPERVISOR:	Ruth Oulton, Henkjan Gersen

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ABSTRACT

Recent developments in photonic crystal research have linked photonic multilayer effects in specialised chloroplasts to photosynthesis for the first time. This investigation provides a novel take on the subject, by identifying photonic crystal ultrastructures composed of stroma lamellae and stroma, in mesophyll chloroplasts of two sugar cane cultivars (*Saccharum officinarum* Vars. F172 & YL6). FFT image analysis was implemented to confirm observed structural periodicity. Transfer matrix method analyses of sugar cane transmission electron microscope images were compared with idealized theoretical crystal structures, from which it was determined that observed disorder does not eliminate photonic effects in sugar cane samples. Mean peak reflectance values of 13.2% and 10.2% were calculated for F172 and YL6 respectively. Disorder in layer position was determined to be of ‘correlated’ type, and independent of peak wavelength λ_{max} in produced spectra. A discussion of the limitations of methods used is provided. Incident spectra, absorption peak magnitudes and mesophyll chloroplast morphology provide three separate explanations linking sugar cane photonic multilayers to a photosynthetic enhancement function.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The spectrum of electromagnetic radiation reflected or emitted by a surface is defined as colour. The reflected component is known as non-emissive colour. The two pathways for the production of non-emissive colour in nature are pigment colour and structural colour[1]. Pigments and dyes absorb a discrete wavelength-range of light, reflecting a reduced spectrum determined by the chemical structure of pigment molecules. Structural colour is the phenomenon where wavelength-scale periodic ultrastructures interfere with a specific incident spectrum, producing reflectance, transmittance and absorptance optical effects[2]. Structural colour has been the focus of over 300 years of study, with motivation stemming from a desire to deconstruct the physical and optical mechanisms that produce observed brilliant colouration and iridescence[3]. Wide-ranging hypotheses have attempted to relate these phenomena to evolutionary adaptations in plants and animals.

The earliest records of observations of structural colour are found in Robert Hooke's 1665 book *Micrographia*, where he describes the colours of a peacock's feathers[4]. Hooke acknowledged not only the iridescent properties that give peacock feathers their brightness, but another property of structural colour - surface colour and intensity varying as angle of view or illumination (incidence) is altered. In Fig. 1, a photograph of *Begonia pavonina* leaves displays the variation of both intensity and surface colour with angle of illumination, as observed by the camera.

Figure 1: Photograph of multiple leaves of *Begonia pavonina*. In this image, bright blue observed colouration results from reflectance peaks in range $450nm < \lambda < 490nm$ across the selection of leaves. Leaf surfaces closest to normal to the light source (behind camera) reflect light at increased intensity as seen by the observer. Reproduced from [5].

Subsequent research has concentrated predominantly on the animal kingdom, with transmission electron microscopy (TEM) providing the first direct observation of ultrastructures inducing colour production in a range of insect species in 1942[6]. TEM provided a technological breakthrough, with sub-nanometre resolution providing views inside previously unobserved microscopic morphologies (see section 2.6). The first detailed paper on the mechanisms behind iridescence in plants was published on two lycophyte species of genus *Selaginella* by Hébant and Lee (1984)[7]. Photonic multilayers in outer cell walls of epidermal cells were linked to interference effects because the 80nm layer widths satisfied the thickness range required for optical multilayer interference, resulting in observed iridescence. In 2016, a combination of transfer matrix method (TMM) modelling and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) image analysis, provided reflectance measurements which demonstrated the presence of photonic multilayer structures, in specialised iridoplast organelles in leaves of *Begonia* species[8]. Iridoplasts contain periodic triple thylakoid membrane stacks separated by stroma, with long-range order providing the consistent layer spacing required for the production of photonic effects. Quantum yield measurements determined that the photonic multilayer possesses a possible function of photosynthetic enhancement, opening the door to bio-engineering applications across *Plantae*.

Previous research into *Begonia* multilayers has not accounted for disorder in individual layer widths. Width disorder in iridoplasts is considered to be 'correlated', with short-range structural order. Increasing variation in layer widths reduces long-range order across a multilayer. From inspection, sugar cane layers have visible short-range disorder (Figs. 7a-d), in contrast with *Begonia* [8]. For this reason, it is important to investigate and quantify the impact of disorder on the photonic effects of these structures. Understanding the impact of variance in individual layer widths on reflectance spectra is critical in concluding whether naturally-forming multilayers can be considered PCs.

Photonic multilayer structures have never been discovered in crop plants. To combine novel findings of photonic effects in crop cultivars with quantum yield measurements promises wide-reaching applications in genetically modified (GM) crop science and agricultural biotechnology. This research project had an emphasis on investigating optical wavelength reflectance effects, due to GM crop applications of enhanced photosynthetic yield. Recent attempts at enhancing photosynthetic crop yield include the Realizing Increased Photosynthetic Efficiency (RIPE) project, founded in 2012[9]. As of yet, research strategies for enhancing photosynthetic efficiency have centred around plant physiology, gene

expression and computational modelling of chemical reaction pathways[10]. Characterization of photonic multilayer ultrastructures in crop cultivars have the potential to provide a breakthrough in crop engineering research.

The main ambition of this research project was to combine image analysis and TMM modelling to uncover evidence of photonic effects in *Saccharum officinarum* (sugar cane) crop cultivars. By generating reflectance spectra as a function of wavelength, to be compared with perfect model crystals, a determination of whether sugar cane chloroplasts contain natural PC structures was attempted. A secondary aim was to explore the effect of disorder on organic multilayers, in comparison with model PC structures. From these calculations, relationships between peak reflectance and variance were explored. Further analysis investigated the relationship between variance measurements in alternating layer compositions.

2. THEORY

2.1 Photosynthesis and Chloroplasts

Photosynthesis is a multi-step reaction through which carbon dioxide, water and light energy are converted into oxygen and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate, a high-energy concentration protein that is converted to glucose or other sugar molecules in the Calvin cycle[11]. Photon absorption by a photosystem (PS) excites electrons along electron transport chains for downstream reactions.

Photosynthesis takes place in flattened organelles called chloroplasts (Fig. 2a), which house thylakoids (fluid-filled cavities) that are stacked into grana. Grana are linked by thylakoid membrane sheets called lamellae. Interconnected grana stacks are surrounded by an aqueous fluid called stroma, where Calvin cycle reactions take place. In sugar cane cultivars *Saccharum officinarum* *Vars. F172* and *YL6*, grana lamellae, which constitute the grana stacks, are surrounded by multilayers of alternating stroma lamellae and stroma layers (Fig. 2b). The ‘absorbing layers’ which contain pigments that absorb incident light are found in thylakoid membranes (Fig. 2a) and stroma lamellae (Fig. 2b). In regular chloroplasts, stroma lamellae are dispersed and rarely form multilayers beyond three layers. *F172* grana extend all the way from upper to lower organelle surface membranes (Figs. 7a, d), unlike regular, compact chloroplast grana (Fig. 2a). Sugar cane is a C_4 crop, meaning it produces four-carbon compounds (malates) during photosynthesis reactions[14]. This is achieved by replacing familiar catalysing enzyme RuBisCO with

Figure 2: Comparison of ultrastructures of ‘regular’ chloroplasts and *Saccharum officinarum* *Vars. F172* & *YL6* chloroplasts. **a** Internal structure of a regular chloroplast, with dispersed stroma lamellae between grana. Reproduced from [12]. **b** Cross-section of a grana-stroma lamellae multilayer complex as found in sugar cane chloroplasts. The grana lamellae (GL) and stroma lamellae multilayer (SLML) are interconnected, sharing membrane surfaces. Stroma lamellae (SL) and stroma (S) are annotated. λ denotes SLML periodicity. The 3D model is compared with cropped TEM of *F172* in control conditions, with λ determined from FFT analysis to be 235.2 ± 17.3 nm. Adapted from [13].

phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase (PEP). As a result, energy-inefficient photorespiration is avoided in photosynthesis reactions, and water loss through stomata on leaf undersides is reduced. The advantages of C_4 carbon fixation make these species suitable for maximising photosynthetic yield in plants, and ideal targets for GM crop experimentation.

2.2 Photonic Crystals

2.2.1 Crystal Structure

In plants, structural colour is either produced from fixed or variable structures[15]. One example of a fixed structure is the photonic crystal. Fig. 3 displays photonic crystals in 1-3 dimensions, with different coloured bands representing periodic λ -scale layers of alternating dielectric constant (refractive index). The real part of the refractive index regulates the transmission of light, whereas the imaginary component determines absorption rates. Both real and imaginary parts regulate reflectance. In 1D, optical path length of reflected waves will depend on the thicknesses and refractive indices of individual layers, as well as angle of incidence and polarisation of light. In order to streamline analysis, all measurements in this project were taken with normal angle of incidence, and calculations were independent of polarisation. Resulting optical effects include the photonic band gap (PBG) which can act as a narrow-band filter corresponding to sharp reflectance peaks, a key identifier of photonic multilayer activity and a main focus of the results of this project. Angular-dependent spectra within a wavelength range (iridescence) is a clear consequence of the dependence of effective optical path length on angle of incidence. An ideal structure for observing these effects can be described as a ‘quarter-wave stack’, where individual layers have width $\frac{n\lambda}{4}$. As a result, constructive and destructive interference occur when layer widths are equal to $\frac{n\lambda}{2}$ and $n\lambda$ respectively. At the boundary between two layers of differing refractive index, light waves are transmitted or reflected. Fig. 4 displays possible light wave paths through a multilayer. The exponential increase in permutations of light wave vectors, and hence electric field components, makes geometric solutions to such problems extremely complex. Computational methods are hence required to solve these problems.

Figure 3: Illustrations of 1-D, 2-D and 3-D photonic crystals, with band colour representing different dielectric constant (c.f. refractive index) values. Parameter Λ denotes period length. Adapted from [16].

Figure 4: Example permutations of light wave travel through layers of alternating refractive index n_1 and n_2 , with possible transmission or reflection at each interface. Following initial reflections, red lines represent transmission towards the surface of the multilayer (up) and black dashed lines represent reflection towards deeper material layers (down). Reproduced from [17].

Photonic crystals are the optical analogue of electronic crystals, whereby rather than containing electrons in a periodic potential, photons interact with a periodic refractive index that alternates in each successive layer[18]. A shared feature of these crystals is measurable band gaps. The physical origin of PBGs is the periodicity of the crystal - no electromagnetic modes are permitted to have frequencies in the gap. Wavelength ranges transmitted and reflected at a boundary represent modes and band gaps respectively. There are two possible mode orientations corresponding to a band gap in a PC. The modes can be positioned at the centre or edge of the Brillouin Zone (BZ). When incident photons have wavelength corresponding to multiples of half the BZ width, wavevector \mathbf{k} is a multiple of width $\frac{BZ}{2}$. Degeneracy arises at the edge of the BZ, and the energies of the two possible modal patterns split, defining the band gap energy. Modes just below the gap have more of their energy concentrated in high- ϵ regions, giving a lower frequency than the next band (Fig. 6).

2.2.2 Crystal Absorption

This understanding of PC structure can now be linked to the absorption enhancement of light in chloroplasts. When the spacing between crystal layers approximately generates a quarter-wave stack (to maximise PBG width), and photons have energy close to the band gap energy, the ‘slow light’ interaction occurs[19]. For wavelengths at the edge of the PBG, interference of incident and reflected waves produces standing waves, because the group velocity of the wave packet reduces to zero. Localised electric field intensity is at a maximum

E field mode orientations for a standing wave pattern

Figure 5: Schematic diagram displaying the two possible mode orientations associated with the first band gap in a 1D photonic crystal for wavevector $k = \frac{\pi}{a}$. Refractive index varies between blue and green layers. Red sinusoidal lines represent the electric field strength for a photon travelling through the multilayer. Adapted from [16].

Local energy density profiles for a standing wave pattern

Figure 6: Schematic diagram demonstrating the variation in energy density profiles between mode patterns positioned over high and low refractive index layers. Electric field energy density concentration in blue ($\epsilon = 13$ F/m) layers is energetically favourable compared with green ($\epsilon = 1$ F/m) layers. Bottom and top images represent successive eigenenergies of the system. Adapted from [16].

at anti-nodes and a minimum at nodes in the standing wave pattern. Increased electric field intensity causes an increase in the absorption of light at these anti-nodes. In chloroplast photonic multilayers, this mechanism could increase photon absorption rates. A different method of visualising the slow light mechanism is to approach the phenomena from reciprocal space (dispersion band diagrams). At the centre and edges of the BZ, the dispersion relation flattens out until the gradient is zero. As dispersion band curvature is inversely proportional to effective mass, the waves travel with zero group velocity at these positions. The two possible modal patterns are displayed Fig. 5. These modes correspond to the first band gap in a 1D photonic crystal, with wavevector $k = \frac{\pi}{a}$, where a is the crystal lattice spacing. Only these alignments are allowed because any other orientation would violate unit cell symmetry about its centre.

Standing wave conditions correlate to acute absorption peaks in reciprocal space at the edge of the band gap.

For optical light absorption to occur, multilayer period Λ must satisfy a discrete sub-micron range. Previously investigated photonic multilayer structures in genii *Begonia* and *Selaginella* revealed whole period widths of 170 ± 20 nm and 130 ± 7 nm respectively [8][20]. The standard multilayer in *Begonia* iridoplasts is composed of grana, containing triple thylakoid membrane stacks of higher refractive index ($n = 1.50 \pm 0.12$ in wavelength range $410 \text{ nm} < \lambda < 730 \text{ nm}$) separated by lumen with lower refractive index ($n = 1.35 \pm 0.05$) [21]. Jacobs *et al.* (2016) demonstrated that anti-nodes for green wavelengths ($\lambda_1 = 530 \text{ nm}$) and nodes for blue wavelengths ($\lambda_2 = 460 \text{ nm}$) were positioned at the grana, where the thylakoid membranes absorb light, for photosynthetic processes in photosystems PSI and PSII [8]. Jacobs *et al.* established that these relationships directly resulted in the enhancement of absorption of green light and reduction in absorption of blue light. *Begonia* species grow in extreme shade conditions with a reduced incident spectrum that peaks at green wavelengths at approx. $\lambda_{max} = 560 \text{ nm}$. Through enhancement of green light absorption in a low light environment, the photonic multilayer structures of *Begonia* iridoplasts have been postulated to increase the rate of light absorption by thylakoid membranes. Consequently, there is an increase in the efficiency (quantum yield) that absorbed light is used for powering electron transport in photosystems, and so the overall efficiency of photosynthesis reactions. Furthermore, the iridescent blue colouration of *Begonia* leaves results from localised decreased electric field strength magnitudes at grana nodes, corresponding to strong reflectance peaks at the edge of the PBG [22]. Angular dependent spectroscopy confirms that the blue leaf colouration is caused by interference effects in the photonic multilayer, because blueshift of the reflectance peak is observed with increasing angle of incidence.

UV photonic crystals have been linked to photoprotective mechanisms in leaves [23]. In the case of sugar cane, the periodicity of stacked grana lamellae is 30 ± 10 nm, too small to produce optical effects at visual wavelengths. Investigation at these wavelengths is not possible with the available TEM images due to pixel resolution limitations (Table I). Adjacent to grana lamellae are the multilayers to be investigated, composed of stroma lamellae (high n) and stroma (low n). Figs. 7a-d represent the four TEM images analysed in this research project, all displaying these multilayer structures of interest. As photosynthetic processes occur in stroma lamellae similarly to thylakoid membranes, photosynthetic functions should be considered when determining the evolutionary purpose(s) of these potentially photonic multilayer structures.

Figure 7: **TEM Images of sugar cane under drought stress (x30000)** a F172 in control 70% soil water capacity conditions. b F172 in mild drought 65-70% soil water capacity conditions. c F172 in severe drought 45-65% soil water capacity conditions. d YL6 in control 70% soil water capacity conditions. *Ch* chloroplast, *GL* grana lamella, *W* cytoderm, *PD* plasmodesma, *C* intercellular spaces. Adapted from [24].

The variational theorem is required in order to understand why localised absorption occurs in *Begonia* thylakoid membranes. The theorem states that the lowest modes of a system have electric field energy concentrated in areas of high dielectric constant[16]. The variational theorem of electromagnetism is analogous to the variational principle of quantum mechanics. The principle applies to Hermitian operators, by taking the weighted average of the eigenvalues of these operators. As electric field is inversely proportional to permittivity, the lowest energy modes have a maximised electric field

at maximum permittivity (i.e. thylakoid membranes in *Begonia*; stroma lamellae in sugar cane). Given that refractive index depends on relative permittivity as $n \propto \sqrt{\epsilon_r}$, the two variables are interchangeable in the definition of the variational theorem.

To complete the picture of localised absorption in thylakoid membranes, it is important to interpret the distribution of electric field energy in the Fig. 6 multilayers. A change in refractive index between layers of a multilayer results in concentration of field energy of both bands in high permittivity layers. Fig. 6 displays

the variation in field energy distribution between modes positioned over different bands. Green and blue layers correspond to permittivity magnitudes $\epsilon = 1$ F/m and $\epsilon = 13$ F/m[16]. In order to minimise the energy functional (to return the lowest energy mode), energy is concentrated into the high refractive index layers at the low wavelength edge of the PBG. Consequently it is energetically favourable to concentrate electric field energy into the blue layers, under the condition that this mode pattern remains orthogonal to the previous mode pattern, rather than store energy in the layers of lower refractive index. This process materialises as broadened energy density peaks spreading into the blue layers in Fig. 6. Following from these mechanisms, the localised increase in electric field and electric field energy required for enhanced absorption of incident light in *Begonia* thylakoid membranes (and possibly sugar cane stroma lamellae) is achieved.

2.3 Transfer Matrix Method

Introduced by Yeh *et al.* (1987), the Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) is used to produce theoretical reflectance spectra[25]. Otherwise near-impossible to solve geometrically, TMM splits interface interactions into many separate problems, to then be substituted into a final transfer matrix. Maxwell's equations predict continuity conditions for an electric field intersecting a boundary between two media of varying refractive index[26]. Propagating light waves are partially reflected and transmitted at successive media through the multilayer, with subsequent interacting wave profiles interfering destructively or constructively. The lamellae/stroma multilayer in sugar cane chloroplasts can be simulated by representing boundary planes with transmission matrix \mathbf{D}_m , and intra-layer light propagation with propagation matrix \mathbf{P}_m . Index m denotes the position of individual layers. TMM was selected as the method for calculating electric field components over the Prum-Fourier method. When compared directly, the Prum-Fourier method has been determined to lack the optical precision required to model sub-micron scale ultrastructures. For *Begonia pavonina* \times *grandis*, the Prum-Fourier method returned reflectance spectra with wavelengths reduced from experimental data by factor 0.89[27].

Localised electric field amplitudes immediately either side of a boundary plane are related by the transmission matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{m-1}^r \\ E_{m-1}^l \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{D}_{m-1,m} \begin{bmatrix} E_m^r \\ E_m^l \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where superscripts l and r represent the direction of

E field vectors pointing left or right from the reference frame of Figs. 5, 7. The transmission matrix can be described in terms of reflection and transmission coefficient magnitudes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{m-1}^r \\ E_{m-1}^l \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{t_{m-1,m}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & r_{m-1,m} \\ r_{m-1,m} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_m^r \\ E_m^l \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where Fresnel coefficients ($t_{m-1,m}$, $r_{m-1,m}$) include refractive index information for designated layers. For near-normal incidence, light polarisation does not need to be accounted for because usage of (r_p , t_p) and (r_s , t_s) yield identical results. Electric field amplitudes at either limit of layer width are described as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_m^r \\ E_m^l \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{P}_{m-1,m} \begin{bmatrix} E_{m'}^r \\ E_{m'}^l \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

with primed and non-primed layer positions representing positions immediately displaced from the left and right layer boundaries. The propagation matrix is defined using travelling plane waves:

$$\mathbf{P}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(i\delta_m) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(i\delta_m) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $\delta_m = 2\pi kn_m d_m$, with d_m denoting layer width. k represents the wave vector (proportional to refractive index). Through multiplication of N_Λ individual layer matrices, a final equation including all electric field components is formed. For a system with light waves crossing two boundaries, this is represented as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{m-2}^r \\ E_{m-2}^l \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{M}_{m-2,m} \begin{bmatrix} E_m^r \\ E_m^l \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_{m-2,m}$ represents the system transfer matrix in the two-boundary case.

2.4 Refractive Indices

Refractive index n is a complex vector, with the imaginary part governing absorption. Only the real part is required for a transparent structure[28]. However in our case, the plant actively controls absorption rates. The incident plane waves can be described as $e^{-i(kx - \omega t)}$, with kx representing the spatial wave component. The real part of the refractive index can be extracted by setting the imaginary component to -1. The passage of a beam of light through a material can be described by Beer's Law with the term e^{-kx} , where k is the adsorption coefficient. This term defines a measure of unit absorbance of a light beam passing through a known material depth[29]. The

intensity at a point within the chloroplast can then be defined in terms of the nominal intensity:

$$I(x) = I_0 e^{-kx}, \quad (6)$$

where I symbolises wave intensity. Complex refractive index is written in the form:

$$\underline{n} = n + i\kappa, \quad (7)$$

where κ represents the extinction coefficient. Absorption/extinctions coefficients and refractive indices vary across the investigated wavelength range (410nm $\leq \lambda \leq$ 720nm). As the only available refractive index data was not successfully implemented into TMM code, mean refractive index values across this range were set as constant at $\underline{n}_{sl} = 1.5 + 0.15i$ (stroma lamellae) and $n_s = 1.3$ (stroma), based on graphical data from Paillotin *et al.* (1993) [21]. Stroma is an aqueous solution, so was assumed to be of similar refractive index to water ($n_w \approx 1.3$) [30]. It is hypothesised that stroma refractive indices fluctuate with time due to varying chemical composition and localised photosynthetic reaction pathways (Kirchhoff, 2014) [31]. In living plants this data is dynamic and unpredictable, with ‘accurate’ refractive index values considered unknown [32]. Consequently, these approximations do not limit accuracy of calculations to the same degree as an approximation from a known data-set. This approximation was further justified by considering that the main aim of the project was to determine whether or not sugar cane chloroplast structures can be photonic multilayers. $\leq 20\%$ variation in refractive indices was demonstrated to have negligible impact on reflectance spectra shape/position, with PC criteria (section 4) fulfilled using these approximations.

2.5 Disorder

Multilayer disorder can be split into two classes - correlated and uncorrelated [33]. Correlated disorder is derived from closely packed/stacked systems which may exhibit short-range order, but one layer of different thickness decreases long-range order. Correlated disorder of layer position x_m and thickness d_m can be described with:

$$x_m = x_{m-1} + \Lambda + \delta x_m, \quad (8)$$

$$d_m = d_{m-1} + \delta d_m, \quad (9)$$

where Λ represents the 1D PC period. δx_m is a randomly generated number distributed uniformly between $-\Delta\Lambda$ and $\Delta\Lambda$, with Δ representing the degree of

disorder. Correlated disorder is known to enhance light localisation near band edges [33], resulting in increased absorption at PBG boundaries for chloroplasts with PC structures. Position disorder causes the transmission dip in the PBG to become shallower and wider, broadening the wavelength range at which light absorption can occur, but decreasing the associated peak reflectance.

In contrast, uncorrelated disorder is not defined by the position/size of adjacent layers:

$$x_m = m\Lambda + \delta x_m, \quad (10)$$

$$d_m = d + \delta d_m. \quad (11)$$

PBGs are more robust in the presence of uncorrelated disorder due to maintenance of long-range order. Uncorrelated disorder is known to cause a divergence in light localisation (measured by the corresponding ‘localisation length’) near PBG edges [33]. Uncorrelated position disorder also causes the transmission dip in the PBG to become shallower at half the rate of correlated position disorder. Quantifying, and hence determining which class of disorder the sugar cane multilayers most closely resemble, would help improve attempts to code multilayer structures accurately.

2.6 TEM Preparation

Microscopy techniques operating on a nanometre scale are required to produce images revealing the ultrastructures of cell organelles. Optical microscopy has a sub-micron resolution limit (≈ 200 nm), blurring multilayer boundaries and making single layer width measurements impossible [34]. In comparison, TEM has sub-nanometre resolution capabilities, suitable for detailed analysis of macromolecular and crystalline morphologies of chloroplasts [35].

To produce imagery, a chemical fixing process is applied to the leaf samples. A consequential limitation of this method is structural damage and shrinkage of the sample, which can eliminate photonic effects from TMM spectra produced [27, 36-38]. For the sugar cane TEM images analysed in this project, leaf samples were suspended in 2.5% (v/v) glutaraldehyde solution and 1% osmic acid, with a 0.1 molar phosphate buffer applied at each stage. Dehydration is also required so that the sample can be embedded in plastic media - when preparing the Fig. 7 samples, epoxy resin mixture Epon812 was applied [24]. This step requires the water content of the sample to be replaced with ethanol, and then propylene oxide for further dehydration. Without dehydration,

Figure 8: **Cross-section visualisations.** **a** Annotated TEM image of F172 in control 70% soil water capacity conditions depicting the position and direction of the 10 multilayer cross-sections. Each transect perpendicularly intersects $N_{\Lambda} = 9$ periods of stroma lamellae/stroma bilayers. Adapted from [24]. **b** Schematic diagram comparing the relative layer widths between cross-sections in **a** and uniform model layers. Short-range order and long-range disorder describe the array of transects, matching a prediction of correlated disorder (section 2.5).

polymerization of the embedding material would occur, and the sample structure would not withstand the vacuum conditions inside EM apparatus[39]. Shrinkage can be accounted for by determining a shrinkage factor, proportional to the shift in spatial period and hence shift in reflectance peak observed in spectra (see section 4)[27].

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1 Image Analysis

Image processing software Image-J was chosen for the image analysis section of the investigation as several different methods for layer width data collection could be attempted. The primary requirement for the software was to provide width data for alternating stroma and stroma lamellae layers that accurately represented both the mean periodicity of the multilayer structure and the disorder within it.

Image-J was used to set the scale of uploaded TEM images, converting the number of pixels along the scale bar to nanometres. Cross-sections were drawn with the line tool perpendicularly across layers, with an average of $N_{\Lambda} = 11$ periods for *Saccharum officinarum*. Fig. 8a displays 10 cross-sections across the TEM image of *Saccharum officinarum* var. F172 at the control of

70% soil water capacity. All transects intersect $N_{\Lambda} \geq 9$ periods of the multilayer. Cross-section direction was always perpendicular to boundary planes. Ensuring normal light wave travel eliminated the requirement for more complex calculations that would take into account varying angle of incidence (e.g. finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) analysis). Fig. 8b compares relative layer widths from the cross-sections with uniform model values, with black and white layers representing stroma lamellae and stroma respectively. Layer widths display short-range ($N_{\Lambda} \leq 2$ periods) order and long-range disorder, following predictions by Liew *et al.* (2010)[33].

Choice of cross-section position was limited by the resolution of the image. In order to collect 10 data-sets, a combination of cross-sections were measured from the surface of, or internally contained within the chloroplast. Variation in orientation of successive cross-sections did not have an impact on results because angle of incidence of light waves was not taken into account in this 1-dimensional ray tracing experiment. Experimental data could then be displayed through reflectance vs wavelength plots generated by TMM.

Layer position measurements were extrapolated from relative intensity plots generated through the 'Plot Profile' function in Image-J (Fig. 9). As pixel resolution varied in range 39.1-43.5nm between Figs. 7a-d (Table I), the shape of sugar cane intensity profiles appeared

as sinusoidal, as opposed to a square wave that would be generated with infinitesimal resolution. This sinusoidal pattern has then been distorted by resolution limitations so that the plot profile appears as a ‘zig-zag’ shape, inducing uncertainties in λ_{min} and λ_{max} values and hence boundary planes. Boundary positions were selected as being at the mid-point between adjacent maxima (stroma, white in Fig. 8b) and minima (stroma lamellae, black in Fig. 8b), as these points intersect the theoretical square wave. Tables III-VI display all boundary width data corresponding to the four TEM images analysed in Figs. 7a-d. Boundary position data were inserted into a list in TMM code.

Figure 9: Relative intensity graph for a cross-section of 6 periods of stroma lamellae/stroma layers in F172 (control conditions), generated with the Plot Profile function in Image-J. The impact of image resolution (39.1nm) limitations on subsequent data collection appear as a ‘zig-zag’ plot shape, inducing error on maxima/minima wavelengths and hence boundary positions.

2D Fast Fourier Transforms (2D FFTs) were applied to the scaled images as an alternative image analysis method, in order to determine the mean periodicity of the multilayers across one image. 2D FFTs decompose the image into a 2D Fourier power spectrum, which is represented in spatial Fourier axes[40]. The main advantage of this method is accurate periodicity determination, achieved at the limit of microscope resolution. Moreover, this method is more efficient than the cross-section method because the FFT decreases the number of waveforms required to be analysed per iteration. However, the compromise from this technique is the restricted range of waveform data to be transformed. Thus a window weighting function needs to be applied in order to compensate for spectral leakage[41]. Scaled images were cropped into squares so that subsequent FFTs produced were not deformed. The native FFT function was applied to the images, with ‘Red/Green’ colour enhancement selected to reveal clustered frequency information (Fig. 10). The arrow in Fig. 10 points to the peak intensity spatial frequency cluster

(black), corresponding to a periodicity of 235.2 ± 17.3 nm in Fig. 7a. This visual evidence of structure periodicity implies photonic effects are likely in the multilayer. Other clusters in the top left quadrant of the FFT are overestimates of periodicity, resulting from blurring of multiple layers into one in the centre of the TEM image.

Figure 10: FFT of *Saccharum officinarum* var. F172 in control conditions. Arrow points towards spatial frequency peak cluster (black), denoting periodicity in the original image (Fig. 7a) in the direction from FFT origin to the highlighted cluster. This spatial frequency intensity peak corresponds to $\Lambda = 235.2 \pm 17.3$ nm. All frequency information is reflected about the origin.

Scholarly literature search engine Google Scholar and cell image libraries were utilised to find candidate chloroplast TEM images for this research. A complete list of all ≈ 50 species, cultivars, and gene expressions investigated is displayed Tables VII-IX. A targeted approach through identification of key words that returned the greatest number of candidate images resulted in 20 plant and 7 algae species being identified for further analysis. TEM images of proplastids/etioplasts with immature ultrastructure were discounted, because observed photonic effects could be eliminated following development to a ‘functional’ mature chloroplast[42]. Immature chloroplasts proved to be a common false positive in the search for novel photonic multilayers. The search was further narrowed down, by removing candidates with multilayer periodicity outside a range corresponding to peak optical reflectance values of 7%+

($100\text{nm} \leq \Lambda \lesssim 250\text{nm}$). Following this process, sugar cane cultivars F172 and YL6 remained as the only two novel candidates fulfilling declared photonic multilayer criteria (see Section 4), and were chosen as advantageous for further investigation over other previously known candidates, due to potential applications in genetic engineering and solar cell technologies[43]. The final four TEM images chosen for further analysis are displayed Figs. 7a-d.

3.2 Transfer Matrix Method

The TMM code run using Python in this project was adapted from a package written by Steven Byrnes freely available online[44]. Several parameters were varied in the code in order to produce reflectance spectra. Individual layer width data for a single cross-section was inserted into a list. Compared with previous TMM analyses of *Begonia* iridoplasts, which used the FFT method to produce “assumed constant thylakoid membrane and lumen thickness[es]”, the inclusion of individual layer width data in reflectance spectra code provided increased precision of model calculations[27]. The code included another list which provided alternating refractive index values per layer. Mean complex refractive index vectors for stroma lamellae, and real refractive index values for stroma (stated in section 2.4) were selected. Light polarisation was arbitrarily chosen as p-polarised, as one polarisation was required to be selected. Reflectance spectra were printed, accompanied with peak reflectance magnitudes and corresponding λ_{max} values. Reflectance spectra were calculated as the relative intensity ratio of reflected and incident waves. 10 cross-sections were taken for each cultivar-humidity combination tested. Mean reflectance spectra were calculated by averaging across all 10 individual spectra per cultivar-humidity combination. This experimental data was then compared with model sugar cane spectra in order to directly see the impact of disorder on photonic properties of the multilayers in Figs. 7a-d. Model sugar cane spectra were produced by coding for a ‘perfect’ crystal with average lamellar and stroma widths 130nm and 100nm. For *Begonia* spectra, literature values for average stroma and thylakoid stack widths of 125nm and 65nm were inserted[8].

4. RESULTS

4.1 Reflectance Spectra and Disorder

In this research project, 10 cross-sections were traced per TEM image for ‘drought-resistant’ sugar cane cultivar *Saccharum officinarum* var. F172 at varying soil humidity parameters. The variation in humidity conditions between images was included because the original experiment from which TEMs were sourced investigated the impact of drought stress on mesophyll chloroplast structure[24]. The humidity ranges imaged were 70%, 65-70%, 45-65%, and 25-45%, representing control, mild drought, moderate drought and severe drought conditions respectively. Figs. 7a-d represent the four TEM images analysed. A total of 40 sets of cross-sectional data were inputted into TMM to produce an equivalent number of reflectance spectra.

Figure 11: Compilation of 10 individual reflectance spectra for *Saccharum officinarum* var. F172 in control humidity conditions of 65-70% soil water capacity. Peak reflectance values range from 9.7-19.7% (Lines 1, 6). A common central maximum is shared between the cross-sections, with average peak reflectance wavelength $636.5 \pm 30.0\text{nm}$.

An example set of 10 individual cross-section reflectance spectra is illustrated in Fig. 11, for F172 in control conditions. Peak reflectance values vary in range 9.7-19.7%. Alternating peaks (6-9% reflectance) and troughs (0% reflectance) in wavelength range $160\text{nm} \leq \lambda \leq 260\text{nm}$ result from higher orders of n wavelengths satisfying quarter-wave stack conditions required for interference effects.

In searching for direct evidence of photonic effects, two main spectral features are predicted. Firstly, a central maximum with peak reflectance $\geq 7\%$. This value was chosen for two reasons. Reflectance spectra produced for all species measured (Tables VII-IX) featured average peak reflectance values $\geq 3\%$. For measured peaks in

range 3-7%, the central peak did not exceed subsidiary peaks by more than a factor 1.5, i.e. the peak was not clear and could be unrelated to photonic effects (and so these plot shapes do not satisfy the second criterion, below). The other, less quantitative reason 7% was chosen, was because the smallest published spectral peak from photonic multilayers in plants is this value[45].

Figure 12: Comparison reflectance spectra plot for *Begonia* uniform model (blue), sugar cane uniform model (green) and sugar cane experimental model (yellow) data. Begonia uniform model spectra produced using layer widths 125nm and 65nm for stroma and thylakoid membranes respectively[8]. Sugar cane uniform model spectra produced using layer widths 130nm and 100nm for stroma lamellae and stroma respectively. Sugar cane experimental model averaged across all F172 control individual cross-section spectra. From left to right, peak reflectance magnitudes: 22.0%, 17.5%, 13.2%.

The average spectra for F172 (control) is displayed Fig. 12 (yellow line), with peak reflectance 13.2% satisfying the first criterion. This value is smaller than the sugar cane uniform model photonic crystal peak of 17.5% (Fig. 12). The difference between these peaks can again be interpreted as the effect of correlated disorder on photonic effects, whereby variation in light path length between successive boundaries increases across an entire multilayer. The difference in λ_{max} (588.0nm vs 636.5 ± 30.0 nm for uniform model and average F172 respectively) could be attributed to the disparity in period lengths $\Lambda_{model} = 230$ nm and $\Lambda_{F172} = 235.2 \pm 17.3$ nm. An improved model with $\Lambda_{model} = 235.2$ nm may return closer λ_{max} values to F172 experimental data. A linear relationship between Λ and λ_{max} was determined (increasing period width increases reflectance peak wavelength i.e. wider layers push spectra to the right). The Fig. 12 Begonia uniform model peak of 22.0% matches the 22% peak calculated with angular reflectance measurements by Jacobs *et al.*[8]. Layer values for Begonia thylakoid and stroma widths were taken from this research paper.

This TMM result is significant, because it indicates accuracy of transfer matrix method results to published experimental spectroscopy results, when inputting the same parameters. Experimental Begonia data is not included in Fig. 12 because required TEM images were not available. Ultimately, the role of Begonia in this experiment was to act as a model photonic crystal, with dimensions as accurate as possible to crystals found in nature. This model could then be compared with spectra produced from real sugar cane data, as a tool to help verify whether sugar cane multilayers can be considered PCs. When comparing model peaks in Fig. 12, the Begonia uniform model peak (22.0%, blue) is greater than the sugar cane uniform model peak (17.5%, green) by a factor 1.26. An explanation for this difference is found by looking at the proportional difference in layer widths within each model. As stated in section 2.2.1, constructive and destructive interference occur when layer widths are equal to $\frac{n\lambda}{2}$ and $n\lambda$ respectively. As Begonia layer widths 125nm/65nm for stroma/thylakoid layers are near multiples, the optical conditions for interference effects are more closely met than for sugar cane (130nm/100nm for lamellae/stroma).

A statistical analysis of cross-section layer widths depicted Figs. 13a-b was attempted so that a relationship between photonic effects and layer disorder could be provided. Variance and standard deviation calculations were applied to data-sets. Variance was selected as the measure of disorder because resulting graphical relationships appeared clearer than when standard deviation was plotted. Independent population variance measurements for (only) stroma lamellae layers and (only) stroma layers were calculated. For *Saccharum officinarum var. F172* in control conditions, disorder in the two layer types are plotted Fig. 13a. A positive correlation of gradient 1.20 ± 0.18 signifies that the layers are not linearly independent i.e. increased variance in one layer type increases variance in the other. The ratio of mean stroma:stroma lamellae layer widths of 1.3 (represented in Fig. 8b by the model cross-section white:black width ratio of 1.3) is within this gradient range, implying that variance scales with layer width. Clustering of data points at the bottom left of Fig. 13a at stroma lamellae/stroma width variance ranges $98\text{nm}^2 \leq \sigma^2 \leq 153\text{nm}^2$ and $58\text{nm}^2 \leq \sigma^2 \leq 153\text{nm}^2$ respectively, demonstrate precision in disorder data across trials. This shows that disorder along cross-sections varies little throughout the chloroplast topography. Furthermore, consistent multilayer shape provides PC structures not only in layers immediately beneath the chloroplast surface, but across the chloroplast ultrastructure. If observed multilayers evolved primarily for their photonic properties, then cross-sections taken as many as $N_{\Lambda} \geq 30$ periods from the nearest organelle surface (see Fig. 8a, cross-sections 6-7) may also be specialised for

Figure 13: **Disorder Plots.** **a** Comparative population variance plot between stroma and stroma lamellae for *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in control conditions. A positive correlation of gradient 1.20 ± 0.18 implies the alternating layers are not linearly independent. Linear fit line intercepts x-axis at $14.8 \pm 0.9 \text{ nm}^2$. Clustering of data points at stroma lamellae/stroma width variance ranges $98 \text{ nm}^2 \leq \sigma^2 \leq 153 \text{ nm}^2$ and $58 \text{ nm}^2 \leq \sigma^2 \leq 153 \text{ nm}^2$ respectively demonstrate precision in disorder data across trials. **b** Peak reflectance as a function of stroma lamellae width variance for *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in severe drought conditions. A negative correlation implies increasing disorder decreases reflectance intensity. Peak reflectance declines from 14.2% to 7.2% in stroma width population variance range 89-746nm.

enhanced light absorption.

Understanding the relationship between quantified disorder and peak reflectance would allow for conclusions to be drawn over whether sugar cane multilayers can be described as photonic. Fig. 13b shows a negative correlation between peak reflectance spectra and stroma width variance for *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in severe drought conditions (Fig. 7d). With increasing layer width disorder, a decrease in peak reflectance is expected due to the disruption of layer boundaries which set the conditions for optical path length shifts in light interference. Within the stroma width variance range displayed (Fig. 13b), peak reflectance declines from 14.2% to 7.2%. As all measured peak reflectance values exceed the first PC criterion of $\geq 7\%$, the structure can be considered photonic. As correlated disorder is characterised by short-range structural order, increasing variation in individual layer widths causes the observed decrease in reflectance maxima. However, all other attempted peak reflectance-variance plots across cultivar conditions yielded no clear correlation as seen in Fig. 13b. As a consequence the possibility of this graph being anomalous must be considered. Further collection of cross-sectional disorder data would strengthen disorder relationship hypotheses, but this was not possible within the project time-frame.

The second main expected feature of PC reflectance spectra is a singular central maximum. In Fig. 15,

no secondary maxima are recorded because subsidiary maxima and minima observed in individual data-sets in range $160 \text{ nm} \leq \lambda \leq 260 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 11) cancel in average spectra plots (Figs. 12, 15). This is important because although UV photonic effects may be recorded via TMM calculations with a single cross-section, nanometre-scale variation between different cross-section layer positions cancel out these effects.

4.2 Shrinkage

The main limitation of data collection using TEM is shrinkage of the sample (see section 2.6). As the scaling for *Begonia sizemoreae* had been corrected for 68.9% shrinkage, no further error needs to be considered for *Begonia* data in Fig. 12[27]. However, the percentage shrinkage of samples is not known for the sugar cane TEM images studied in this project. Accounting for shrinkage in λ_{max} determination is pivotal to accurately identify what colour is being produced by the multilayer. Fig. 14 displays the impact of shrinkage on F172 control reflectance spectra in 10% increments. The shape of the plots remained near-identical with minute peak broadening at increasing shrinkage (wavelength). In Fig. 14, this is visible from the relative intersections of adjacent peaks, which increased from 10-11% from left to right. Maxima magnitudes of $636.5 \pm 30.0 \text{ nm}$, $700.0 \pm 30.0 \text{ nm}$, $763.5 \pm 30.0 \text{ nm}$ and $827.5 \pm 30.0 \text{ nm}$ for successive increases in shrinkage (left to right) were

4.3 Drought

Figure 14: The impact of speculative shrinkage values on reflectance spectra for *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in control conditions of 70% soil water capacity. Yellow, green and red lines represent 10%, 20% and 30% shrinkage respectively. λ_{max} values of 636.5 ± 30.0 nm, 700.0 ± 30.0 nm, 763.5 ± 30.0 nm and 827.5 ± 30.0 nm were recorded for successive increases in shrinkage (from left to right).

Figure 15: Comparison plot of average reflectance spectra for sugar cane cultivars F172 (control, blue; mild drought, yellow; severe drought, green) and YL6 (control, red). In this order, mean peak reflectance values of 13.2%, 13.4%, 6.9% and 10.2% were recorded, at λ_{max} magnitudes of 636.5 ± 30.0 nm, 620.5 ± 30.0 nm, 578.0 ± 30.0 nm and 605.5 ± 30.0 nm respectively (Table II). Observed plasmolysis (i.e. increasing correlated disorder) with increasing drought through Figs. 7b-d result in decreasing peak reflectance.

recorded. Consequently, a proportional relationship between shrinkage factor and λ_{max} is concluded.

The influence of drought conditions on photonic effects is represented in Fig. 15. Understanding the impact of drought on the shape of multilayers will give insights into the practicality of PC function in a highly dynamic environment. This is made especially relevant during the ongoing climate crisis, where localised drought conditions are increasingly common worldwide[46]. Average reflectance plots for all four cultivar-environment combinations tested were calculated by taking the mean average of 10 cross-section data-sets. As seen in Fig. 15, structural disorder increases with increasing drought strength. Between successive stages of drought, water loss from the plant cell (and hence chloroplast) causes a decrease in plant cell and organelle volume. Reductions in chloroplast length of 33.2% and 35.6% were recorded between control and severe drought conditions for cultivars F172 and YL6 respectively[24]. In drought conditions, previously highly ordered lamellae stacks contract in order to remain within the boundaries of the chloroplasts, requiring a crumpling effect in layers, marginally visible in Figs. 7b-c. This process is defined as plasmolysis[47]. In increasing drought conditions, chloroplasts experience decreasing short-range order, but maintain long-range order sufficiently to produce singular, central maxima of $\geq 7\%$, indicative of PC spectra.

One result in Fig. 15 that contradicts this trend is the peak reflectance value of F172 in mild drought conditions (13.4%) exceeding the control peak (13.2%). Furthermore, the mild drought peak is a factor 2 wider than all other compared peaks. One explanation for these results is random error in TEM methods. As different chloroplasts were analysed for each humidity condition, variation in disorder between individual chloroplast structures would alter reflectance spectra shape. From inspection, the F172 TEM image for mild drought conditions (Fig. 7b) displays increased disorder between adjacent layers, compared with the image taken in control conditions (Fig. 7a). Resulting reflectance spectra match predictions of correlated disorder by Liew *et al.* (2010), which find that increasing correlated order of layer positions widens PBG peaks[33]. Maxima wavelengths in range $578.0\text{nm} \leq \lambda_{max} \leq 636.5\text{nm}$ are displayed in Table II. The trend of decreasing λ_{max} with increasing drought reflects the loss of volume and hence compaction of chloroplast multilayers during plasmolysis.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Image Analysis

TEM image pixel resolution was the predominant source of systematic error faced in the image analysis section of the project, because data collected from cross-sections directly impacted reflectance spectra dimensions. Sugar cane image pixel resolution varied in range 39.1nm (Fig. 7a) to 43.5nm (Fig. 7c) (Table I). Relative intensity plots produced by cross-sections returned sinusoidal wave patterns. As layer widths were calculated from midpoints between intensity, a square wave pattern would provide minimal error. Consequently, layer width errors of 21.1nm to 23.8nm were encountered, when accounting for random error of ± 2 nm per boundary position determination. Image-J was used in an attempt to improve pixel resolution. FFTs produced from Fig. 7a had all frequency information removed using the circle tool, below the threshold spatial frequency range $217.94\text{nm}/c \leq \nu \leq 252.49\text{nm}/c$ relating to the periodicity of the scaled image (see the peak intensity cluster in Fig. 10). Another attempt to improve pixel resolution was to remove unnecessary frequencies and generate an inverse FFT. The inverse FFT produced had decreased resolution, with intensity varying within only 48% of the previous plot range i.e. the range of intensity values in Fig. 9 were reduced, making determination of layer boundary positions more difficult. This increased errors introduced in layer boundary identification, and hence inverse FFT analysis was not used prior to spectra production. Following these circumstances, a threshold resolution below which inverse FFT analysis is beneficial for analysis of Fig. 7 images may be determinable.

Although the FFT method was originally intended for mean period measurements of TEM images, the cross-section method was deemed advantageous for analysis of the Figs. 7a-d sugar cane images because consecutive stroma and stroma lamellae layers varied with average standard deviation $\sigma = 15.24\text{nm}$ and 17.37nm respectively, across the four images. As the FFT method only provided a single average periodicity value for an image, reflectance spectra did not account for disorder in layer thickness. The cross-section method has the capability to produce multiple spectra per image (Figs. 8a, 11), from which average spectra can be produced that account for variation within the chloroplast ultrastructure (Figs. 12, 15). One functionality which may enhance future data collection is the ability to choose which regions within the multilayer to analyse, preventing unwanted structures e.g. grana lamellae ('GL', Figs. 7a-b, d) from disrupting periodicity computation.

5.2 Transfer Matrix Method

The largest source of systematic error experienced using the TMM method was peak wavelength error of $\pm 30\text{nm}$. This value was calculated by looking at the average spread of individual reflectance peaks (Fig. 11) from F172 and YL6 images in control conditions (Figs. 7a, d). The impact of this error on drawing conclusions is reduced confidence determining what optical colour is being produced by the structures, and which pigments are potentially absorbing this light. For example, the 60nm error range between 570nm and 630nm-wavelength light stretches from yellow to red on the optical spectrum (Fig. 16). Furthermore, chlorophyll a/b and PSI/II red peaks are all spread within a 60nm range, making identification of a specific pigment attributed to light absorption unclear[48]. A second source of systematic error was wavelength iterations at 0.5nm intervals, contributing error $\pm 0.5\text{nm}$ to all wavelength values mapped. The impact of this error does not alter the λ_{max} magnitudes enough to be detected as a colour change by the human eye, so this error is negligible when hypothesising possible functions of the multilayer based on colour production. One improvement to the TMM method used would be to insert continuous refractive index data as a function of wavelength, improving accuracy of modelled layers compared with real parameters in leaves[21].

5.3 Cross-section Method

One limitation of the cross-section method is the assumption that line intersections are perpendicular to multilayers throughout the transects. Macroscopically, ultrastructures vary in orientation throughout the chloroplasts (Fig. 8a), but adjacent stroma lamellae can also vary in position by up to 15° . Accounting for this orthogonality assumption would require introducing a new type of angular disorder. Trigonometric analysis shows that orientation shift of $\pm 15^\circ$ returns a $\pm 3.4\%$ error in layer width compared with a parallel boundary composition. As errors introduced are short-range, and are estimated to only occur at angles $\leq 10^\circ$ per cross-section, the effect on corresponding reflectance spectra is negligible. One method to overcome this limitation would be to utilise the segmented line tool in Image-J to ensure orthogonality to boundaries is always achieved. However, the cross-section now becomes 2-dimensional, and light polarisation/angle of incidence can no longer be ignored. This is rectified by using FDTD analysis ('Yee's method'), within which light polarisation/angle

of incidence are included in simulations[49].

An assumption made regarding the composition of the chloroplast was that no disruption to the stroma lamellae/stroma sequence of multilayer occurred throughout all cross-sections. Components such as starch globules and plastoglobuli are dispersed randomly throughout chloroplasts, but have diameters above the resolution limit of the TEM images studied (Table I), so are avoided when drawing cross-sections[50]. However, ribosomes and chloroplast ‘B’-DNA have widths 20nm and 2nm respectively, below the resolution limit. As these chloroplast components do not have functions requiring light absorption, incident light waves would likely either be reflected or transmitted. These extra layers unaccounted for within photonic multilayers would have a no noticeable effect of reflectance spectra, based on TMM simulations with several randomly dispersed 20nm wide layers. These components could influence adjacent layer refractive indices, but as discussed in section 2.4, refractive index variation has a negligible effect on reflectance spectra shape and magnitude.

A further assumption taken concerning the ‘slice’ observed by TEM is the orthogonality between microscope lenses and multilayer boundaries. If the multilayer were rotated about the z axis (pointing through the multilayer) by angle ϕ , all layer widths would be varied by the same factor, calculated trigonometrically like the adjacent layer orientation shift discussed previously. Consequentially, disorder is not being introduced to the system. As any offset from a right angle between multilayer and lens would reduce apparent layer widths, produced spectra may be underestimates of real trends. An idea of the quantitative impact induced is shown by the shrinkage plots (Fig. 14), where the percentage change in magnification is proportional to the change in spectra wavelength, i.e. a 1.5% reduction in apparent layer widths arising from a 10° slice offset would decrease average sugar cane spectra in Figs. 12, 15. Overall, the impact of adjacent layer rotation reduces peak reflectance of spectra. The effect of slice rotation stretches spectra to the left (λ_{max} reduces), while conversely, increasing shrinkage stretches spectra to the right (λ_{max} increases). Accounting for all these factors is critical in producing accurate spectra from which conclusions can be drawn.

5.4 Pigments

Pigments chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b are both present in this cultivar. Chlorophyll a exhibits absorption maxima at $430\pm 10\text{nm}$ and $665\pm 10\text{nm}$ (dark blue/red) (Fig. 16)[51]. Chlorophyll b displays absorp-

Figure 16: Absorption spectra for common sugar cane chloroplast pigments chlorophyll a (filled line), chlorophyll b (dashed line) and accessory pigment β -carotene (dotted line). Chlorophyll a absorption peaks are found at $430\pm 10\text{nm}$ (dark blue) and $665\pm 10\text{nm}$ (red). Chlorophyll b peaks are found at $460\pm 10\text{nm}$ (blue) and $642\pm 10\text{nm}$ (red). β -carotene peaks are found at $440\pm 10\text{nm}$ (dark blue) and $475\pm 10\text{nm}$ (light blue). Adapted from [51].

tion peaks at $460\pm 10\text{nm}$ and $642\pm 10\text{nm}$ (blue/red). Also displayed in Fig. 16 is the absorption spectrum of β -carotene, an ‘accessory pigment’, which absorbs incident light and then re-transmits that light energy to other pigments directly involved in photosynthesis reactions. β -carotene has absorption maxima at $440\pm 10\text{nm}$ (dark blue) and $475\pm 10\text{nm}$ (light blue). Photosystems are also candidate pigments for light absorption. PSI/II are modified versions of chlorophyll a, widespread in electron transport chains. Average peak reflectance of $636.5\pm 30.0\text{nm}$ for F172 in control conditions results in orange/red colour production (Fig. 16). Absorption peaks found 50-100nm after reflectance peaks in chloroplasts imply an average absorption peak in range $711.5\pm 55.0\text{nm}$. The absorption peak range overlaps chlorophyll a, the most widely distributed pigment in most plant species. As the absorption peak spectra range also overlaps the PSI/II peaks at $700\text{nm}/680\text{nm}$ respectively (Fig. 16), a PC structure may function as enhancing red light absorption for downstream pigment absorption, implying a possible photosynthetic function. Previous research has determined that PSI protein complexes are located with increased relative concentration in stroma lamellae, whereas PSII com-

plexes are more concentrated in grana[52-55]. As the absorbing layers of the structures being investigated are composed of stroma lamellae, this reinforces the hypothesis that F172 multilayers are adapted for PSI absorption. Average peak reflectance of 605.5 ± 30.0 nm for YL6 in control conditions results in yellow, orange or red colour production. Both PSI/II and chlorophyll a/b peaks fall within YL6 estimated absorption peak range 680.5 ± 55.0 nm (red light absorption). β -carotene peaks lie ≥ 140 nm from the nearest cultivar peak range (Fig. 16), so the multilayer is not specialised for accessory pigment absorption. Future modelling of absorption spectra could narrow down the candidate pigments associated with light absorption for these cultivars.

5.5 Shrinkage

The effect of shrinkage on pigment absorption can be analysed by comparing reflectance peaks, to the chlorophyll absorbance spectra, displayed in Fig. 16. Although the cited *Begonia sizemoreae* shrinkage value of 68.9% far exceeds the plotted range of 0-30%, larger shrinkage factors were deemed unrealistic in the source article of TEM images analysed [24, 36]. The possibility of shrinkage being accounted for before scale bars were applied would eliminate the requirement for shrinkage corrections. Projected absorption peaks for shrinkage parallax errors 10% (775.0 ± 55.0 nm), 20% (838.5 ± 55.0 nm) and 30% (902.0 ± 55.0 nm) (Fig. 14) stretch beyond any chlorophyll a/b, β -carotene or photosystem absorption peaks. Shrinkage-affected peaks lie beyond the near-infrared limit (780nm), meaning for the analysed F172 chloroplasts to have PCs with photosynthetic function, shrinkage is required to have been accounted for before scale bars were labelled. Infra-red photonic crystals have been linked to gas detection applications[56-57]. In plants, carbon dioxide and oxygen levels are regulated to optimise photosynthesis reactions. Guard cell receptors are known to detect internal carbon dioxide concentration, and close stomata (openings on underside of leaves) if concentration increases beyond 0.4%[58]. However, this gas detection mechanism is not understood, with competing theories arguing that the mechanism is related to Ca^{2+} , pH and malate, or zeaxanthin levels[59-63]. Mesophyll chloroplast infrared photonic multilayers may provide an alternative mechanism theory, if the samples analysed experienced 10-30% shrinkage during the TEM investigation.

5.6 Evolutionary Arguments for Photonic Multilayers

Multiple theories have attempted to link PC structures in plants to an evolutionary function. Jacobs *et al.* (2016) determined that *Begonia* iridoplasts were likely specialised to enhance photosynthesis in extreme shade conditions[8]. Chlorophyll fluorescence imaging (CFI) measurements determined quantum yield (the efficiency with which absorbed light is used for photosynthesis and electron transport) enhancement of 5-10% in these conditions, further supporting the link to photosynthetic yield. An opposing hypothesis proposes that blue-leaf iridescence is a photoprotective mechanism. Shade-adapted plants “would be extremely vulnerable to photodamage if even transiently exposed to sun-flecks”, due to the sensitivity of adapted photosystem reaction pathways[64]. In *Begonia*, strong reflectance peaks in blue wavelength range $400\text{nm} \leq \lambda \leq 485\text{nm}$ indicate a damage reduction mechanism, or prevention of excessive irradiation, which in turn could inhibit photosynthesis (Lee *et al.*, 2008)[23]. However in the case of sugar cane, organisms are directly exposed to the full ground-level solar spectrum. This means sugar cane cultivars are more likely to be adapted to bright incident light, making a photoprotective specialisation less crucial for survival compared with *Begonia*. Evolutionary adaptations tend to deliver a net benefit to the organism, so individual adaptations can be constrained by trade-offs[66]. A third explanation to be considered is that the multilayers did not evolve for photonic applications. As the compact multilayer structures seen in Figs. 7a-d pack the surrounding organelle volume, the chloroplast may be filling the interior with efficiently ordered stacks, in order to maximise photosynthetic rates by conventional pigment absorption. As these chloroplasts are of mesophyll morphology, known to be adapted to maximise photosynthetic rates across *Plantae* species, they may ‘already’ be specialised for conventional photosynthesis[67]. Another non-photonic explanation can be unpicked by looking at the grana lamellae (‘GL’) in Figs. 7a, d. Unlike chloroplasts in most species, these stacks of thylakoids stretch all the way from one chloroplast surface to the other. As the stroma lamellae is known to function as the ‘skeleton’ of the chloroplast, a ‘wall-to-wall’ grana stack may require an extended stroma lamellae multilayer (imagine an extended version of Fig. 2b). However, this argument could be flipped on its head. If stroma lamellae layers are ordered for photonic absorption effects, the argument that grana evolved to grow across an organelle width, to act as a series of anchor points for stroma lamellae photonic multilayers, should be considered (Fig. 2b).

Mesophyll chloroplasts, from which TEM images were analysed, are known to be specialised in C4 plants for

the light dependent reactions of photosynthesis[14]. If future research confirms the existence of PCs in C4 crops for the first time, a new explanation for the mechanisms specialising these chloroplasts will be uncovered. Estimated absorption peak ranges, based on reflectance spectra produced in this investigation, traverse the PSI/II and chlorophyll a absorption maxima (F172) and PSI/II and chlorophyll a/b absorption maxima (YL6). This experimental evidence bolsters the photosynthetic enhancement evolutionary theory, and therefore is currently the prevailing explanation for the existence of photonic multilayers in sugar cane mesophyll chloroplasts. Further work (using new TEM images) focused on producing TMM absorption plots to confirm absorption λ_{max} values, coupled with reflected light microscopy and angular reflectance analyses, would supply necessary proof of photonic effects. Light intensity spatial distribution calculations could confirm that localised electric field intensities superimpose stroma lamellae as required. CFI measurements to calculate quantum yield would contribute a direct link between photonic effects and photosynthesis. Finally, these analyses should be extended across to bundle sheath cell chloroplasts, which may exhibit different characteristics.

6. CONCLUSION

This project pursued thorough research into the reflectance effects of a pair of previously uninvestigated *Saccharum officinarum* cultivars F172 and YL6. Average F172 and YL6 reflectance data satisfied the two main spectral features predicted for PCs. Firstly, central maxima of peak reflectance 13.2% and 10.2% respectively exceed the 7% threshold required for verifiable photonic effects. Secondly, a singular central maximum was detected in all F172 and YL6 cross-sections attempted. Disorder between individual layer widths was determined to not disqualify the analysed structures from being considered PCs. Disorder was determined to be correlated, characterised by short-range structural order and long-range disorder.

Advantages and limitations of the FFT and cross-section methods were compared, with the cross-section method concluded to be favorable due to the additional functionalities of individual layer width measurements and transect spatial selectivity. Pixel resolution was the largest source of systematic error in the research, but intensity profile approximations allowed photonic spectra to be analysed. TEM slice orthogonality and adjacent layer rotation were compared in a comprehensive method error analysis.

Cultivar absorption peak estimations were matched

with pigment absorption peaks, with average F172 absorption peak range traversing the PSI/II and chlorophyll a absorption maxima, and average YL6 peak range crossing PSI/II and chlorophyll a/b absorption maxima. The cross-over between multilayer and photosystem absorption peaks implies a photosynthetic evolutionary function in sugar cane chloroplasts. Two further identified arguments for this theory are direct sunlight exposure, and mesophyll chloroplast morphology.

A proposed future research pathway is to reproduce the methodology used by Jacobs *et al.* (2016), for an extensive range of sugar cane cultivars in place of *Begonia* species[8]. Confirmed identification of photonic crystal ultrastructures in mesophyll sugar cane chloroplasts promises real-world applications in GM crop bio-engineering[47]. Aside from enhancing photosynthetic yield, utilisation of multi-level agricultural crop distribution through manipulation of transmission, reflectance and absorption properties of photonic crystals promise breakthroughs in plant cultivation management.

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Table IV: Layer width data for 10 cross-sections of *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in mild drought conditions. Successive columns denote adjacent layers. Multilayers with $6 \leq N_\Lambda \leq 12$ layers are described. *St La* Stroma lamellae, *St* stroma.

Sugar Cane F172 [Mild Drought]

Cross-section no.	St La	St	St La																						
1	167	141	110	87	103	115	117	107	143	151	123	78	102	119	131	130	122	130	110	113	117				
2	163	111	110	117	96	94	101	112	129	153	136	101	188	121	132	143	125	103	107	121	112	116	105	105	128
3	151	124	103	100	113	91	112	147	139	106	114	112	117	105	111	91	101	101	93	120	120				
4	145	116	95	109	139	140	138	143	114	102	105	116	115	113	117	134	125	90	92	70	129				
5	131	151	140	108	110	112	122	127	105	110	109	136	116	117	118	150	104	115	107	114	96	77	88		
6	138	123	124	154	108	89	86	110	124	112	119	116													
7	106	122	110	122	103	104	138	123	119	111	104	77	107	127	133										
8	136	113	118	73	100	100	103	120	103	99	136	118	127	87	120										
9	144	110	111	106	109	114	115	116	102	74	118	127	115	71	146										
10	128	154	124	103	115	114	132	157	116	104	117	103	112	94	136	133	119	94	122						

Table V: Layer width data for 10 cross-sections of *Saccharum officinarum* var. *F172* in severe drought conditions. Successive columns denote adjacent layers. Multilayers with $8 \leq N_\Lambda \leq 11$ layers are described. *St La* Stroma lamellae, *St* stroma.

Sugar Cane F172 [Severe Drought]

Cross-section no.	St La	St	St La	St																				
1	125	129	124	118	124	144	123	117	115	125	141	114	135	133	127	119	121							
2	134	124	120	124	158	152	142	136	117	79	96	91	96	101	104	107	115	123						
3	112	116	130	102	118	62	104	125	146	122	213	135	155	131	125	109	145							
4	138	90	105	97	119	123	107	121	119	113	118	142	134	133	144	145	155	138						
5	133	140	119	143	174	176	134	112	125	123	123	126	165	174	148	113	120	119	146					
6	123	137	129	138	171	145	132	122	121	124	133	110	128	125	166	191	152	127	139	128	137	154		
7	127	125	170	203	158	138	130	111	119	128	140	159	129	117	141	154	173	175	152	129	125			
8	140	120	123	137	189	187	176	162	157	125	130	119	143	154	164	148	175							
9	131	130	131	138	182	140	143	136	162	132	151	149	145	166	175	143	152							
10	118	105	132	126	131	135	163	135	120	119	136	161	115	73	120	117	127	138	148	148	167			

Table VI: Layer width data for 10 cross-sections of *Saccharum officinarum* var. *YL6* in control conditions. Successive columns denote adjacent layers. Multilayers with $7 \leq N_\Lambda \leq 12$ layers are described. *St La* Stroma lamellae, *St* stroma.

Sugar Cane YL6 [Control]

Cross-section no.	St La	St																							
1	107	112	125	108	92	91	110	128	107	110	105	107	95	91	113	116	118	123	126						
2	92	88	90	97	99	106	100	93	105	118	122	87	115	114	123	106	109	119	117	85	98	117	125		
3	88	104	135	104	129	110	115	97	114	110	119	100	102	114	94	80	108	119	119	117	120	77	115	110	126
4	93	87	102	102	111	105	114	104	110	92	104	122	104	98	80	118	123	93	108	115					
5	131	117	112	121	106	108	117	142	132	132	115	132	96	52	121	137	110	87	116						
6	107	102	109	92	101	117	107	116	137	145	115	115	111	84	110	112	106	118							
7	108	94	121	110	117	129	152	77	83	114	108	112	101	103	114	125	130	104	120	95	117	121	147		
8	142	87	100	118	143	147	131	121	118	91	108	98	132	128	131										
9	135	120	130	116	129	155	138	136	141	132	108	120	122	126	139										
10	100	101	96	107	103	116	118	106	128	149	127	92	105	82	113	98	122	106	121	101	92	96	116		

Classification of Analysed Species			
Species/Cultivar/Environmental Condition	Mature Chloroplasts	Optical PC Periodicity	PC Reflectance Spectra
C4 Grasses			
<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> (Sugar cane)			
- Var. F172 'Control'	✓	✓	✓
- Var. F172 'Mild Drought'	✓	✓	✓
- Var. F172 'Severe Drought'	✓	✓	✓
- Var. YL6 'Control'	✓	✓	✓
- Var. B41227 "Grey Hog"	X	-	-
<i>Zea mays</i> (Maize)			
- Wild Type 'Control'	✓	X	-
- Wild Type '80% Soil Humidity'	✓	X	-
- Wild Type 'Phosphorus-Deficient'	✓	X	-
- Wild Type 'Infected with Maize Mosaic Virus (MMV)'	✓	X	-
Shade-dwelling Plants			
<i>Begonia sizemoreae</i>	✓	✓	-
<i>Begonia rockii</i>	✓	✓	-
<i>Selaginella erythropus</i>	✓	✓	-
<i>Trichomanes elegans</i>	✓	✓	-
<i>Phyllagathis rotundifolia</i>	✓	X	-
Diatoms			
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	✓	✓	X
<i>Achnanthes minutissima</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Attheya ussurensis</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Aulacoseira baicalensis</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Chaetoceros muelleri</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Stephanopyxis turris</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Synedra acus</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Thalassiosora proshkinae</i>	✓	X	-

Table VII: List of plant and algae species for which TEM images were analysed in search of photonic crystal structures. 'Mature chloroplasts' criteria ticked if imaged organisms had fully matured organelles. Etioplasts/protoplastids are a common false positive for PC identification from TEM literature. 'Optical PC Periodicity' criteria ticked if average periodicity across multiple image cross-sections was in range $100\text{nm} \leq \Lambda \leq 250\text{nm}$. Periodicity values were determined using the line tool in Image-J. Minimum range value 100nm was selected to allow for estimated $\leq 30\%$ shrinkage of samples. Above $\Lambda \approx 250\text{nm}$, PC structures enter the infra-red regime. 'PC Reflectance Spectra' criteria ticked if produced spectra satisfy the two conditions for photonic multilayer reflectance spectra described in section 4. '✓' denotes criteria satisfied. 'X' denotes criteria not satisfied. '-' denotes no further investigation conducted. " " denotes colloquial nomenclature. ' ' designates environmental condition. Analysed images were obtained from [24, 27, 67-78].

Classification of Analysed Species (cont.)			
Species	Mature Chloroplasts	Optical PC Periodicity	PC Reflectance Spectra
Trees			
<i>Picea engelmannii</i> “Engelmann Spruce”	✓	✓	X
<i>Cupressus macrocarpa</i> “Monterey Cypress”	✓	✓	X
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> “Maidenhair Tree”	✓	✓	X
<i>Populus</i> × <i>canescens</i> “Grey Poplar”	✓	X	-
Herbs			
<i>Flaveria bidentis</i> “Coastial Plain Yellowtops”	✓	✓	X
<i>Flaveria bidentis</i> “Speedyweed”	✓	X	-
<i>Callisia fragrans</i> “Basket Plant”	✓	X	-
<i>Nicotiana rustica</i> “Aztec Tobacco”	✓	X	-
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> “Basil”	X	-	-
Legumes			
<i>Glycine max</i> “Soybean”	✓	✓	X
C3 Grasses			
<i>Brassica campestris</i> “Field mustard”	✓	✓	X
<i>Poa alpina</i> Var. <i>vivipara</i>	✓	✓	X
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> “Common wheat”	X	-	-
Aquatic Plants			
<i>Hydrobryum khaoyaiense</i>	✓	X	-
<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i>	X	-	-
<i>Ottelia alismoides</i> “Duck Lettuce”	X	-	-

Table VIII: List of tree, herb, legume, C3 grass and aquatic plant species analysed as part of a comprehensive literature search for photonic crystal structures in *Plantae*. Three tree species provided periodicity within the required Λ range, but all images had short- and long-range structural disorder, returning no peaks in average reflectance plots. Analysed images were obtained from [79-93].

Classification of Analysed Species (cont.)			
Species/Environmental Condition/Gene Expression	Mature Chloroplasts	Optical PC Periodicity	PC Reflectance Spectra
Flowering Plants			
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> (sorted by gene expression)			
- Wild Type	✓	✓	X
- Wild Type 'at 4° C'	✓	✓	X
- Wild Type 'at 20° C'	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1a-HA curt1a-2</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1ab</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1abc</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1abcd</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1ac</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>curt1b-1</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>stic1-1</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>stic2-1</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>cprabA5e-1 'at 4° C'</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>cprabA5e-1 'at 20° C'</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>cprabA5e-2 'at 4° C'</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>cprabA5e-2 'at 20° C'</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>ppi1</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>sp1 ppi1</i>	✓	✓	X
- <i>ADL1del2</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>Col-0</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>curt1a-2</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>curt1c-1</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>curt1d-1</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>k1k3</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>Ler</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>stn7 stn8</i>	✓	X	-
- <i>tap38-1</i>	✓	X	-
- Wild Type 'de-etiolated'	X	-	-
<i>Amaranthus edulis</i> Speg. "Love-lies-bleeding"	✓	✓	X
<i>Heliotropium texanum</i>	✓	✓	X
<i>Mollugo cerviana</i> "Threadstem Carpetweed"	✓	✓	X
<i>Peperomia pellucida</i> "Pepper Elder"	✓	✓	X
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> "Tomato Plant"	✓	✓	X
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i> "Spinach"	✓	✓	X
<i>Monstera deliciosa</i> "Swiss Cheese Plant"	X	-	-

Table IX: List of flowering plants analysed for PC structures in TEM images of chloroplasts. Curvature in multilayer structures proved the limiting factor in most *Arabidopsis thaliana* samples. *Solanum lycopersicum* provided singular reflectance peaks at 6.4% (303.0nm) and 8.0% (332.5nm) respectively, which may be of interest for future UV PC research in *Plantae*. Analysed images were obtained from [94-104].